

Filtrado no lineal: morfología

Gonzalez & Woods, cap 8.4

- Fundamentada en la teoría de conjuntos: las imágenes se consideran como conjuntos.
 - Imágenes binarias: conjuntos de pixels corresponden a objetos.
 - Imágenes en grises: conjuntos umbra definidos bajo las funciones de intensidad
- Operadores basicos corresponden a filtros no lineales de la imagen basados en los operadores maximo y minimo.

Definiciones básicas

A and B be sets in Z^2

$a = (a_1, a_2)$ and $b = (b_1, b_2)$,

traslación

reflexion

complemento

translation of A by $\bar{x} = (x_1, x_2)$,

$$(A)_x = \{c | c = a + x, \text{ for } a \in A\}.$$

$$\hat{B} = \{x | x = -b, \text{ for } b \in B\}.$$

$$A^c = \{x | x \notin A\}.$$

diferencia

$$A - B = \{x | x \in A, x \notin B\} = A \cap B^c.$$

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 8.25 (a) Set A ; (b) set A translated by point x ; (c) set B ; (d) reflection of B ; (e) set A and its complement; (f) the difference of two sets (shown lined). The dot in each of the first four figures indicates the origin of the set.

Dilatación del objeto A con el objeto estructural B

$$A \oplus B = \{x | (\hat{B})_x \cap A \neq \emptyset\}$$

$$A \oplus B = \{x | [(\hat{B})_x \cap A] \subseteq A\}$$

$$A \oplus B = \{c \in Z^2 | c = a + b, \text{ for some } a \in A \text{ and } b \in B\}$$

Minkowsky addition $A \oplus B = \bigcup_{b \in B} (A)_b$

Figure 8.26 (a) Original set A; (b) square structuring element and its reflection; (c) dilation of A by B, shown shaded; (d) elongated structuring element; (e) dilation of A using this element.

Erosion del objeto A con el objeto estructural B

$$A \ominus B = \{x | (B)_x \subseteq A\}$$

$$A \ominus B = \{c \in Z^2 | c + b \in A, \text{ for every } b \in B\}$$

Minkowsky subtraction $A \ominus B = \bigcap_{b \in B} (A)_{-b}$

Figure 8.27 (a) Original set A; (b) structuring element B; (c) erosion of A by B, shown shaded; (d) elongated structuring element; (e) erosion of A by this element.

Propiedades: dualidad

$$(A \ominus B)^c = A^c \oplus \hat{B}.$$

Demostración:

$$(A \ominus B)^c = \{x \mid (B)_x \subseteq A\}^c.$$

Por la definición de erosión

$$(A \ominus B)^c = \{x \mid (B)_x \cap A^c = \emptyset\}^c.$$

Debido a que $(B)_x \cap A^c = \emptyset$,

Cuando B trasladado por x está incluido en A

$$\begin{aligned} (A \ominus B)^c &= \{x \mid (B)_x \cap A^c \neq \emptyset\} \\ &= A^c \oplus \hat{B} \end{aligned}$$

Por la definición del complemento

Filtros morfológicos básicos: cumplen la propiedad de idempotencia.

Apertura: rompe istmos y elimina protuberancias

$$A \circ B = (A \ominus B) \oplus B$$

Cierre: funde brechas y elimina pequeños agujeros

$$A \bullet B = (A \oplus B) \ominus B$$

Propiedades: dualidad

$$(A \bullet B)^c = (A^c \circ \hat{B}).$$

- (i) $A \circ B$ is a subset (subimage) of A .
- (ii) If C is a subset of D , then $C \circ B$ is a subset of $D \circ B$.
- (iii) $(A \circ B) \circ B = A \circ B$. Idempotencia

- (i) A is a subset (subimage) of $A \bullet B$.
- (ii) If C is a subset of D , then $C \bullet B$ is a subset of $D \bullet B$.
- (iii) $(A \bullet B) \bullet B = A \bullet B$. Idempotencia

Cierre con un objeto circular

Apertura con un objeto
estructural circular.
Dependiendo del radio el
efecto varia.

Caracterización geométrica de la apertura: la apertura es el objeto que resulta de la union de todas las traslaciones del objeto estructural que caben en el objeto. Corresponde a pasar el objeto estructural por el interior de la frontera y eliminar las partes que no son cubiertas.

Interpretación geométrica del cierre: todos los puntos que pertenecen a traslaciones del objeto estructural que tocan. Corresponde a pasar el objeto estructural por el exterior de la frontera y rellenar los huecos a los que no alcanza.

Translates of B containing z . Each intersects A and, therefore, $z \in A \bullet B$

Figure 8.30 Geometric interpretation of closing. Point z , contained in $(B)_x$, belongs to the closing, $A \bullet B$, if and only if $(B)_x \cap A \neq \emptyset$.

Ejemplo de eliminación de ruido mediante filtrado morfológico: la apertura elimina las motas en el fondo y las protuberancias, el cierre elimina los agujeros en el objeto.

Figure 8.31 Morphological filtering: (a) original, noisy image; (b) result of erosion; (c) opening of A; (d) result of performing dilation on the opening; (e) final result showing the closing of the opening. (Adapted from Giardina and Dougherty [1988].)

Trasformación de localización: Hit-or-Miss transform

$$A \circledast B = (A \ominus X) \cap [A^c \ominus (W - X)].$$

$$A \circledast B = (A \ominus B_1) \cap (A^c \ominus B_2).$$

$$A \circledast B = (A \ominus B_1) - (A \oplus \hat{B}_2).$$

Figure 8.32 (a) Set A; (b) a window, W, and the local background of X with respect to W, (W - X); (c) complement of A; (d) erosion of A by X; (e) erosion of A^c by (W - X); (f) intersection of (d) and (e), showing the location of the origin of X, as desired. It is instructive to copy X and (W - X) on tracing paper and run these templates over A and A^c to verify the results in (d) and (e).

Extracción de fronteras en imágenes binarias mediante operadores morfológicos:

La diferencia respecto de la erosión del objeto

La forma del objeto estructural condiciona la frontera resultante

$$\beta(A) = A - (A \ominus B)$$

Figure 8.33 (a) Set A; (b) structuring element B; (c) A eroded by B; (d) boundary extracted by taking the set difference between A and its erosion.

Rellenado de regiones mediante la dilatación condicionada al complementario del objeto a partir de un punto inicial (semilla).

$$X_k = (X_{k-1} \oplus B) \cap A^c \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

$$X_0 = p,$$

Fin de la iteración

$$\bar{X}_k = X_{k-1}$$

Figure 8.34 (a) Set A containing a boundary subset; (b) complement of A; (c) structuring element B; (d) initial point inside the boundary; (e)–(h) various steps of Eq. (8.4-15); (i) final result, obtained by forming the set union of (a) and (h).

Extracción de componentes conexos mediante dilatación condicionada al objeto a partir de una semilla inicial

$$X_k = (X_{k-1} \oplus B) \cap A \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

$$X_0 = p,$$

Figure 8.35 (a) Set A containing one connected component Y and initial point p (all shaded points are valued 1, but are shown different from p to indicate that they have not yet been found by the algorithm); (b) structuring element; (c) result of first iterative step; (d) result of second step; (e) final result.

Envolvente convexo (convex hull) $C(A)$.

$B^i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4$, Objetos estructurales

Secuencias de hit-or-miss condicionadas

$$X_k^i = (X \circledast B^i) \cup A \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad \text{and} \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

$$X_0^i = A. \quad D^i = X_{\text{conv}}^i, \quad X_k^i = X_{k-1}^i. \quad C(A) = \bigcup_{i=1}^4 D^i.$$

Figure 8.36 (a) Structuring elements used in the convex hull algorithm (the \times 's indicate "don't care," and B^i is a rotation of B^{i-1} by 90°); (b) set A ; (c)–(f) results of convergence with the four structuring elements shown in (a); (g) convex hull; (h) convex hull showing the contribution of each structuring element.

Adelgazamiento: thinning $A \otimes B$,

$$A \otimes B = A - (A \circledast B) \\ = A \cap (A \circledast B)^c.$$

$$A \otimes \{B\} = ((\dots ((A \otimes B^1) \otimes B^2) \dots) \otimes B^n).$$

Adelgazamiento simétrico

$$\{B\} = \{B^1, B^2, B^3, \dots, B^n\} \quad B^i \text{ es una versión rotada de } B^{i-1}$$

Figure 8.37 (a) Sequence of rotated structuring elements used for thinning; (b) Set A ; (c) result of thinning with the first element; (d)–(i) results of thinning with the next seven elements (there was no change between the seventh and eighth elements); (j) result of using the first element again (there were no changes for the next two elements); (k) result after convergence; (l) conversion to m -connectivity.

Engorde: thickening

$$A \odot B = A \cup (A * B)$$

Engorde simétrico

$$A \odot \{B\} = ((\dots ((A \odot B^1) \odot B^2) \dots) \odot B^n).$$

cálculo del engorde del objeto a través del adelgazamiento del complementario. Puede necesitar podas adicionales.

Figure 8.38 Thickening via thinning of the background: (a) set A; (b) its complement; (c) result of thinning the complement of A; (d) thickened set obtained by complementing (c); (e) final result, showing removal of disconnected points.

Esqueletos o “medial axis”: puntos equidistantes de la frontera.

$$S(A) = \bigcup_{k=0}^K S_k(A)$$

$$S_k(A) = \bigcup_{k=0}^K \{(A \ominus kB) - [(A \ominus kB) \circ B]\}$$

$(A \ominus kB)$ Indica k erosiones sucesivas con B

$$(A \ominus kB) = ((\dots (A \ominus B) \ominus B) \ominus \dots) \ominus B$$

$$K = \max \{k \mid (A \ominus kB) \neq \emptyset\}.$$

El esqueleto tiene la propiedad de reconstrucción: el objeto se puede reconstruir a partir del esqueleto mediante dilataciones iteradas

$$A = \bigcup_{k=0}^K (S_k(A) \oplus kB)$$

$$(S_k(A) \oplus kB) = ((\dots (S_k(A) \oplus B) \oplus B) \oplus \dots) \oplus B$$

Ejemplo del proceso de cálculo del esqueleto y de la reconstrucción del objeto a partir del esqueleto.

Figure 8.39 An example of the implementation of Eqs. (8.4-24)–(8.4-26). The original set is shown at the top left, and its morphological skeleton is shown at the bottom of the fourth column. The reconstructed set is shown at the bottom of the sixth column.

Poda: eliminación de componentes parasitos.

Objetos estructurales en la secuencia $\{B\}$ que detectan puntos extremos (endpoints)

$$X_1 = A \otimes \{B\}$$

elimina las protuberancias

$$X_2 = \bigcup_{k=1}^8 (X_1 \circledast B^k)$$

Detecta puntos extremos

$$X_3 = (X_2 \oplus H) \cap A$$

Dilatación condicionada de los extremos

$$X_4 = X_1 \cup X_3$$

Resultado final

Figure 8.40 Example of pruning: (a) original image; (b) and (c) structuring elements used for deleting (thinning) end points; (d) result of three cycles of thinning; (e) end points of (d); (f) dilation of end points conditioned on (a); (g) pruned image.

Table 8.3 Summary of Morphological Results and Their Properties

Operation	Equation	Comments ¹
Translation	$(A)_x = \{c c = a + x, \text{ for } a \in A\}$	Translates the origin of A to point x .
Reflection	$\hat{B} = \{x x = -b, \text{ for } b \in B\}$	Reflects all elements of B about the origin of this set.
Complement	$A^c = \{x x \notin A\}$	Set of points not in A .
Difference	$A - B = \{x x \in A, x \notin B\} = A \cap B^c$	Set of points that belong to A but not to B .
Dilation	$A \oplus B = \{x (B)_x \cap A \neq \emptyset\}$	"Expands" the boundary of A . (I)
Erosion	$A \ominus B = \{x (B)_x \subseteq A\}$	"Contracts" the boundary of A . (I)
Opening	$A \circ B = (A \ominus B) \oplus B$	Smooths contours, breaks narrow isthmuses, and eliminates small islands and sharp peaks. (I)
Closing	$A \bullet B = (A \oplus B) \ominus B$	Smooths contours, fuses narrow breaks and long thin gulfs, and eliminates small holes. (I)
Hit-or-miss transform	$A \odot B = (A \ominus B_1) \cap (A^c \ominus B_2)$ $= (A \ominus B_1) - (A \oplus \hat{B}_2)$	The set of points (coordinates) at which, simultaneously, B_1 found a match ("hit") in A and B_2 found a match in A^c .
Boundary extraction	$\beta(A) = A - (A \ominus B)$	Set of points on the boundary of set A . (I)
Region filling	$X_k = (X_{k-1} \oplus B) \cap A^c; \quad X_0 = p$ and $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$	Fills a region in A , given a point p in the region. (II)
Connected components	$X_k = (X_{k-1} \oplus B) \cap A; \quad X_0 = p$ and $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$	Finds a connected component Y in A , given a point p in Y . (I)

Table 8.3 (Continued)

Operation	Equation	Comments ¹
Convex hull	$X'_i = (X'_{i-1} \odot B) \cup A; \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4,$ $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, X'_0 = A,$ and $D^c = X'_{conv}$ $C(A) = \bigcup_{i=1}^{conv} D^c$	Finds the convex hull $C(A)$ of set A , where "conv" indicates convergence in the sense that $X'_i = X'_{i-1}$. (III)
Thinning	$A \otimes B = A - (A \odot B)$ $= A \cap (A \odot B)^c$ $A \odot \{B\} = ((\dots((A \otimes B^1) \otimes B^2) \dots) \otimes B^k)$ $\{B\} = \{B^1, B^2, B^3, \dots, B^k\}$	Thins set A . The first two equations give the basic definition of thinning. The last two equations shown denote thinning by a sequence of structuring elements. This method is normally used in practice. (IV)
Thickening	$A \odot B = A \cup (A \otimes B)$ $A \odot \{B\} = ((\dots((A \odot B^1) \odot B^2) \dots) \odot B^k)$	Thickens set A . (See preceding comments on sequences of structuring elements.) Uses (IV) with 0's and 1's reversed. (IV)
Skeletons	$S(A) = \bigcup_{k=0}^K S_k(A)$ $S_k(A) = \bigcup_{i=0}^k \{(A \ominus kB) - [(A \ominus kB) \circ B]\}$ $A = \bigcup_{k=0}^K (S_k(A) \oplus kB)$	Finds the skeleton $S(A)$ of set A . The last equation indicates that A can be reconstructed from its skeleton subsets $S_k(A)$. In all three equations, K is the value of the iterative step after which the set A erodes to the empty set. The notation $(A \ominus kB)$ denotes the k th iteration of successive erosion. (I)
Pruning	$X_k = A \otimes \{B\}$ $X_2 = \bigcup_{i=1}^2 (X_i \otimes B^i)$ $X_3 = (X_2 \oplus H) \cap A$ $X_4 = X_3 \cup X_1$	X_k is the result of pruning set A . The number of times that the first equation is applied to obtain X_k must be specified. Structuring elements (V) are used for the first two equations. The third equation uses structuring element (I).

¹ The Roman numerals in parentheses refer to the structuring element(s) used in the morphological process (see Fig. 8.41).

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(a)

adaw PL
1 37919-2100

(b)

adaw PL
1 37919-2100

(c)

adaw PL
1 37919-2100

(d)

adaw PL
1 37919-2100

adaw PL
1 37919-2100

Figure 8.42 (a) Thresholded address field; (b) close-up of ZIP code, showing touching and broken characters; (c) result after five iterations of erosion in a box enclosing the touching characters (characters are now disjoint); (d) result after three iterations of dilation on entire ZIP code field (breaks in the leftmost 1 and in the 2 bridged); (e) skeleton of (d), showing parasitic branches in the corner of the 7 and in one of the 0's; (f) result after seven iterations of pruning, showing removal of the parasitic branches. (Courtesy of Perceptics Corporation)

Morfología en imágenes en escala de grises

Se basa en los operadores máximo y mínimo, supone pasar de operar con conjuntos a operar con funciones.

$f(x,y)$ es la función imagen, $b(x,y)$ la función estructural, tienen dominios de definición D_f y D_b .

Dilatación en funciones 1D y 2D (imágenes en escala de grises)

$$(f \oplus b)(s) = \max\{f(s - x) + b(x) \mid (s - x) \in D_f \text{ and } x \in D_b\}.$$

$$(f \oplus b)(s, t) = \max\{f(s - x, t - y) + b(x, y) \mid (s - x), (t - y) \in D_f; (x, y) \in D_b\}$$

Erosión en en funciones 1D y 2D (imágenes en escala de grises)

$$(f \ominus b)(s) = \min\{f(s + x) - b(x) \mid (s + x) \in D_f \text{ and } x \in D_b\}.$$

$$(f \ominus b)(s, t) = \min\{f(s + x, t + y) - b(x, y) \mid (s + x), (t + y) \in D_f; (x, y) \in D_b\}$$

Dualidad de la erosión
y dilatación funcioal

$$(f \ominus b)^c(x, y) = (f^c \oplus \hat{b})(x, y)$$

where $f^c = -f(x, y)$ and $\hat{b} = b(-x, -y)$.

Ilustraciones de la erosión y dilatación funcional en 1D.

Figure 8.43 Dilation obtained by sliding b past f . Mathematically, indexing is easier to implement by sliding f past b . The result, however, is the same. (Adapted from Giardina and Dougherty [1988].)

Figure 8.45 (a) Original image; (b) result of dilation; (c) result of erosion. (Courtesy of A. Morris, Leica Cambridge, Ltd.)

Apertura morfológica en funciones

$$f \circ b = (f \ominus b) \oplus b.$$

Cierre

$$f \bullet b = (f \oplus b) \ominus b.$$

Dualidad apertura-cierre

$$(f \bullet b)^c = f^c \circ \hat{b}.$$

$$-(f \bullet b) = (-f \circ \hat{b}). \quad \text{Because } f^c = -f(x, y),$$

Propiedades de la apertura

- (i) $f \circ b \leftarrow f$,
- (ii) If $f_1 \leftarrow f_2$, then $(f_1 \circ b) \leftarrow (f_2 \circ b)$,
- (iii) $(f \circ b) \circ b = f \circ b$.

Propiedades del cierre

- (i) $f \leftarrow (f \bullet b)$,
- (ii) If $f_1 \leftarrow f_2$, then $(f_1 \bullet b) \leftarrow (f_2 \bullet b)$,
- (iii) $(f \bullet b) \bullet b = f \bullet b$.

$$u \leftarrow v \quad u(x, y) \leq v(x, y)$$

y el dominio de u esta incluido en el de v .

(a)

(b)

Figure 8.47 (a) Opening and (b) closing of Fig. 8.45(a). (Courtesy of A. Morris, Leica Cambridge, Ltd.)

Apertura y cierre
con la misma
función
estructural.

Suavización morfológica que
consiste en aplicar la apertura
seguida de un cierre con el mismo
objeto (función) estructural.

morfología

$$g = (f \oplus b) - (f \ominus b).$$

Gradiente morfológico, útil para detección de bordes. La forma del borde encontrada dependerá del objeto estructural.

$$h = f - (f \circ b)$$

Transformación de sombrero alto (top-hat). Sirve para resaltar detalles en zonas de poco contraste (baja iluminación).

detección de texturas

La apertura y cierre con objetos de distintos tamaños permite diferenciar zonas de la imagen con distintas texturas o contar el número de items (partículas) de cada tamaño (granulometría).

granulometria

